

GAS DRYING AND CONTROL OF HYDRATE FORMATION

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Gas dehydration is a basic gas treatment step that is used in virtually all gas treatment plants to avoid the formation of hydrates in high-pressure natural gases during transportation or during cryogenic gas processing (NGL/LPG recovery, LNG production). Drying is also used to prevent corrosion caused by condensed water in sour gas streams [1].

Typical water dew point values based on the most common gas drying methods are given below:

- For the transportation of natural gas, depending on the geographical region - in the range from 0 °C to -20 °C. However, this temperature may be lower in case of transportation via long underwater gas pipelines.
- For condensate/LPG recovery - between -20°C and -50°C
- For NGL recovery and LNG production, the required residual water content is below 0.1 ppm vol. corresponds to water dew point below -80 °C.

Various technologies are used for gas drying. If the process does not require achieving very low water dew point values, it is advisable to provide methanol supply and drying with silica gel, in particular for gas transport. When lower dew point values are required, as is the case in most cases, glycol dehydration (MEG, DEG and mainly TEG) is provided in the range of -10 °C to -40 °C. In the case of NGL recovery and LNG production, where water dew point values below -80°C are required, molecular sieves can be used [2].

The following is a list of available gas dehydration processes:

Glycol dehydration and regeneration : Glycol dehydration is one of the most common gas treatment technologies.

Triethylene glycol (TEG) is the most commonly used glycol due to its elevated regeneration temperature, which reduces the residual water content of the regenerated glycol and provides lower dew points of the treated gas. **Diethylene glycol** (DEG) and monoethylene glycol (MEG) are also used, but are generally used for the purpose of inhibiting hydrate formation .

There are several different methods for glycol regeneration. As the purity of unsaturated glycol increases, the dew point of the treated gas and the glycol circulation decrease, but the complexity of regeneration increases:

- **Simple evaporation** : only the TEG reboiler is used for regeneration . Typical unsaturated TEG concentration is 98.5 wt%, providing water dew point reductions in the 40°C range.
- **Classic stripping** : a classic stripping column is added. The typical concentration of unsaturated TEG is 99.9% by weight, providing a reduction in water dew points in the range of 70 – 80 °C.
- **Improved stripping** : by increasing the stripping gas flow rate and the complexity of the stripping column, a maximum typical unsaturated TEG concentration of 99.95 wt% is achieved, ensuring a reduction in water dew points in the range of 80 – 90 °C.

Siirtec 's patented glycol regeneration processes Nigi " (DRIGAS™ - ECOTEG™) : using Siirtec 's patented processes Nigi " greater purity and lower dew points can be achieved. The DRIGAS™ process is based on recirculation of regeneration gas, providing very high stripping rates with unsaturated TEG purity of 99.98%, and dew point reduction of the treated gas in the range of 100 °C. The DRIGAS™ process does not require additional solvents. The boil-off gas is recirculated , due to which its consumption is significantly reduced. Operating costs and pollution are reduced.

The ECOTEG™ process is based on a similar design to the DRIGAS™ process and is used for the dehydration of gases rich in aromatic compounds (benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene and xylene), i.e. in the case where the control of pollutant discharges is a critical factor, since there are no emissions of aromatic compounds into the environment. The main advantage of the ECOTEG™ process is the ability to meet more stringent disposal regulations without additional equipment, low operating costs and low gas dew point (similar to the DRIGAS™ process).

Molecular sieve dehydration : Molecular sieves are crystalline, highly porous materials composed of aluminosilicates and characterized by a very large internal surface with high adsorbing properties allowing very low residual water content in the treated gas, typically in the range of 0.1 ppm vol. . up to 1 ppm vol. Molecular sieves can also be used to dry NGLs or light condensate at the ppm level .

Typically, molecular sieves of types 3A and 4A are used depending on the composition of the raw material. In particular, Type 3A is recommended to minimize COS formation when the feed contains CO₂ and H₂S, while Type 5A screens are typically used for NGL dehydration.

A cyclic operating mode is provided; Once the molecular sieve layer is saturated with water, it is regenerated by heating and subsequent cooling to restore its adsorbing capacity. Regeneration is usually carried out in a closed loop scheme, in which the regeneration gas is a stripping of the dried treated gas and is forced through a regeneration compressor.

Silica gel drying : the principle of operation is similar to the use of molecular sieves with a similar installation configuration, however, silica gel ensures that the residual water content in the treated gas is only in the range of 5 to 10 ppm and the dew point is between -40°C and -50°C , which is an intermediate option between the use of glycols and molecular sieves.

Methanol Injection : Methanol injection is typically used for hydrate inhibition and dehydration at wellheads, as well as in multiphase transfer lines, gas pipeline transport, or in LPG or LNG recovery units where moderate dew point values are required. Typical water dew point values range from 0°C to -40°C depending on operating conditions, methanol purity and feed flow. Methanol is characterized by high evaporation losses. However, in some cases, the residual liquid phase of methanol can be recovered by distillation.

References:

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